

Efficacy of Duloxetine and Amitriptyline along with Arthrocentesis In The Management of Temporomandibular Joint Disorders

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Abstract

Temporomandibular Joint Disorders (TMDs) are musculoskeletal conditions affecting the temporomandibular joint (TMJ), commonly resulting in pain, limited mouth opening, joint sounds, and psychological distress. This study aimed to evaluate and compare the efficacy of Duloxetine and Amitriptyline as adjuncts to arthrocentesis in the management of TMD. A total of 10 patients diagnosed with early-stage internal derangement of the TMJ (Wilkes Stage II and III) were randomly divided into two groups. Group I underwent arthrocentesis followed by Duloxetine 20 mg twice daily for 15 days, while Group II received arthrocentesis followed by Amitriptyline 25 mg twice daily for the same duration. Clinical parameters such as pain (VAS score), maximum mouth opening, TMJ clicking, lateral mandibular movement, and psychological status (Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale) were evaluated preoperatively, and at the 7th day and 4th week postoperatively. Both groups showed improvement in symptoms, but Group I demonstrated significantly better outcomes in pain reduction ($p = 0.021$), increased mouth opening ($p = 0.016$), and decreased anxiety levels ($p = 0.021$) at the 4th week. No significant difference was noted between the groups in terms of TMJ clicking and lateral movement. The results suggest that arthrocentesis combined with Duloxetine is more effective than when combined with Amitriptyline in managing TMD symptoms. However, larger studies with extended follow up are needed to further substantiate these findings.

Introduction

The temporomandibular joint (TMJ), also known as the mandibular joint, is a synovial joint that uniquely functions as a bilateral articulation composed of two ellipsoid joints. It is encased in a fibrous capsule and includes essential synovial components such as the synovial membrane and fluid, along with several ligaments that contribute to joint stability. Anatomically, the mandible and the cranium join together to create a unified structural unit, which justifies the accurate anatomical term craniomandibular articulation¹. This articulation shares several classic features with other synovial joints, including the presence of an articular disk, synovial fluid, capsule, and supporting ligaments. Movement within the joint is precisely regulated by the interplay of the joint's osseous morphology, masticatory muscles, supporting ligaments, and the occlusal relationship of the dentition. Owing to the bilateral connection of the mandible, the joints operate in unison and cannot function independently².

The TMJ comprises two distinct anatomical components: the mandibular element, which includes the condylar process and the

mandibular neck, and the cranial element, which encompasses the articular surface of the temporal bone. Other important anatomical landmarks of the joint include the articular eminence, articular tubercle, preglenoid plane, mandibular fossa's lateral boundary, and the glenoid process. Central to the joint is the articular disk - a biconcave fibrocartilaginous structure that facilitates smooth gliding and hinge movements. The entire joint is enclosed within a fibrous capsule and is supported by multiple ligaments including the collateral, sphenomandibular, and stylomandibular ligaments. Lubrication is maintained by synovial fluid, secreted by synoviocytes, which is critical for reducing friction and ensuring smooth movement.

Temporomandibular disorders (TMD) encompass a range of musculoskeletal and functional disorders affecting the TMJ and its associated structures. Common clinical manifestations include joint pain, restricted

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mouth opening, and joint locking². The etiology of TMD is multifactorial and includes systemic, hormonal, mechanical, and parafunctional factors. Advancing age, autoimmune diseases, endocrine imbalances, nutritional deficiencies, metabolic dysfunctions, and infectious diseases can all affect the metabolism of fibrocartilage, compromising the joint's adaptive capabilities. Hormonal influences are particularly noted for their role in remodeling of the condylar region. Mechanical stress, whether due to trauma or malocclusion, can lead to internal derangements and degeneration of the articular cartilage. Microtrauma or macrotrauma to the joint may initiate inflammatory cascades, resulting in chronic pain. Parafunctional habits such as bruxism exert abnormal forces on the joint and can precipitate disc displacements and degenerative alterations. Additionally, emotional and psychological factors such as stress and depression often co-occur with chronic TMJ pain, indicating a biopsychosocial model of TMD pathogenesis³.

Accurate diagnosis of TMD requires a multidisciplinary assessment strategy, incorporating the patient's medical and dental history, clinical evaluation, and radiographic imaging. Clinical examination involves palpation of the joint and muscles, evaluation of mandibular range of motion, and occlusal analysis. Radiographic modalities such as X-rays, MRI, and CT scans provide detailed visualization of both soft and hard tissues within the joint and help in identifying structural anomalies or degenerative changes⁴.

The management of TMD focuses on symptom alleviation, restoration of function, and prevention of progression. Initial treatment options include conservative therapies such as pharmacological management (e.g., NSAIDs, acetaminophen, muscle relaxants, and tricyclic antidepressants), physical therapy, and patient education. Behavioural interventions such as cognitive behavioural therapy, habit reversal, biofeedback, and relaxation techniques are shown to be beneficial, especially in chronic cases. Occlusal splints are widely used due to their reversibility and non-invasive nature; they help in muscle relaxation, TMJ unloading, and protection against dental wear caused by parafunction⁵.

Pharmacologic agents like TCAs and serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs) have shown promise in managing chronic TMD pain. Duloxetine, a centrally acting SNRI, is effective in treating chronic musculoskeletal pain, including that arising from osteoarthritis and TMD. It works by inhibiting the reuptake of serotonin and norepinephrine, key neurotransmitters involved in central sensitization and chronic pain. Similarly, amitriptyline, a tricyclic antidepressant, has demonstrated efficacy at low doses (e.g., 25 mg/day) in managing chronic TMD pain without significant adverse effects. These agents modulate central pain processing and can significantly reduce pain intensity and improve quality of life when used as part of a multidisciplinary treatment plan³.

In patients who do not respond adequately to conservative therapies, arthrocentesis has gained popularity as a minimally invasive surgical intervention. This procedure involves lavage of the upper joint compartment with the aim of breaking intra-articular adhesions and flushing out inflammatory mediators such as interleukins and cytokines. Arthrocentesis improves joint mobility, reduces pain, and restores mandibular function. It is considered a valuable first-line surgical approach before more invasive surgical options are explored⁷.

Objective of the Study

This study aims to evaluate the comparative efficacy of arthrocentesis combined with duloxetine (20 mg) and arthrocentesis combined with a tricyclic antidepressant (amitriptyline) in the management of chronic pain associated with temporomandibular disorders. By comparing these combinations, the study seeks to determine which pharmacological adjunct, when used alongside arthrocentesis, offers superior relief from chronic TMJ pain and improves overall joint function.

Materials and Methods

This prospective randomized clinical study was conducted in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery at Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College & Research Centre, Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh. A total of 10 temporomandibular joints (TMJ) were included and randomly divided into two groups of five joints each, irrespective of the patients' race, sex, caste, or socio-economic status. Group I received arthrocentesis followed by duloxetine 20 mg administered twice daily for 15 days, while Group II received arthrocentesis followed by amitriptyline 25 mg administered twice daily for 15 days. Inclusion criteria comprised patients aged 18 to 70 years with TMJ pain located in the face, jaw, temple, or around the ear during chewing or mouth opening, and diagnosed with Wilke's stage II or III internal derangement. All patients provided informed consent before participation. Patients were excluded if they had a history of TMJ surgery, responded to prior conservative therapy, had joint pathologies, or presented with coagulation disorders.

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS)

Tick the box beside the reply that is closest to how you have been feeling in the past week.
Don't take too long over your replies: your immediate is best.

D		A	
I feel tense or 'wound up':			
3	Most of the time	3	I feel as if I am slowed down:
2	A lot of the time	2	Nearly all the time
1	From time to time, occasionally	1	Very often
0	Not at all	0	Sometimes
I still enjoy the things I used to enjoy:			
0	Definitely as much	0	I get a sort of frightened feeling like 'butterflies' in the stomach:
1	Not quite so much	1	Not at all
2	Only a little	2	Occasionally
3	Hardly at all	3	Quite Often
I get a sort of frightened feeling as if something awful is about to happen:			
3	Very definitely and quite badly	3	I have lost interest in my appearance:
2	Yes, but not too badly	2	Definitely
1	A little, but it doesn't worry me	1	I don't take as much care as I should
0	Not at all	0	I may not take quite as much care
I can laugh and see the funny side of things:			
0	As much as I always could	3	I feel restless as I have to be on the move:
1	Not quite so much now	2	Very much indeed
2	Definitely not so much now	1	Quite a lot
3	Not at all	0	Not very much
Worrying thoughts go through my mind:			
3	A great deal of the time	0	I look forward with enjoyment to things:
2	A lot of the time	1	As much as I ever did
1	From time to time, but not too often	2	Rather less than I used to
0	Only occasionally	3	Definitely less than I used to
I feel cheerful:			
3	Not at all	3	I get sudden feelings of panic:
2	Not often	2	Very often indeed
1	Sometimes	1	Quite often
0	Most of the time	0	Not very often
I can sit at ease and feel relaxed:			
0	Definitely	0	I can enjoy a good book or radio or TV program:
1	Usually	1	Often
2	Not Often	2	Sometimes
3	Not at all	3	Not often
Please check you have answered all the questions			
Scoring:			
Total score: Depression (D) _____ Anxiety (A) _____			
0-7 = Normal			
8-10 = Borderline abnormal (borderline case)			
11-21 = Abnormal (case)			

Figure 1- Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale

All patients were educated about their condition and instructed to avoid excessive jaw movements, including hard biting and gum chewing. Clinical evaluation involved obtaining a complete medical history, informed consent, and performing extra-oral and intra-oral examinations using diagnostic

instruments. Radiographic evaluation using orthopantomogram (OPG) and TMJ open and closed views was carried out to exclude bony pathologies. Each patient was assessed preoperatively and at postoperative intervals (1st and 4th weeks) based on several parameters. Pain was measured using a 10 cm visual analogue scale (VAS), with scores ranging from 0 (no pain) to 10 (severe pain), as described by Singh et al. in 2021. Maximum mouth opening (MMO) was assessed in millimeters between the incisal edges of the upper and lower central incisors using a calibrated ruler, following Nitzan et al. (1991). Lateral and anterior excursive jaw movements were evaluated by measuring the deviation of the lower jaw from the midline of the upper central incisors, as per Yura and Totsuka (2005). TMJ clicking sounds were assessed through clinical palpation during mouth opening and closing and noted as either present or absent, according to the method described by Carvajal and Laskin (2000). Psychological assessment was done using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS), as per Singh et al. (2017), where scores of 0–7 were considered normal, 8–10 borderline, and 11–21 indicative of clinical anxiety or depression.

Arthrocentesis was performed under local anesthesia in a sterile setting. The patient was draped, and the TMJ area was disinfected with povidone-iodine. An auriculotemporal nerve block was given using 2% lignocaine hydrochloride. The Holmlund Hellsing line was drawn from the midpoint of the tragus to the outer canthus of the eye. Two entry points were marked: the first point was 10 mm anterior and 2 mm inferior to the tragus-canthus line, and the second was 20 mm anterior and 10 mm inferior to the same line. Using a 26-gauge needle and 10 ml syringe, lavage was performed using 0.9% normal saline to irrigate the joint and eliminate inflammatory mediators. After irrigation, the needles were removed, and entry points were covered with sterile dressings. Group I patients were then prescribed duloxetine 20 mg twice daily, and Group II patients were prescribed amitriptyline 25 mg twice daily, both for 15 days. Postoperative care included instructions for a soft diet, application of hot and cold fomentation, maintenance of proper sleep, and adherence to physiotherapy exercises. Follow-up assessments were conducted on the 7th and 28th days post-treatment using the same clinical and psychological parameters to evaluate treatment outcomes.

Figure 2- Holmlund Hellsing Line

Statistical Analysis

Data collected during the study were entered in Microsoft Excel 2007 and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage, were used to summarize the data. The level of statistical significance was set at 5% ($p < 0.05$).

To assess data distribution, the Shapiro–Wilk test was applied, while Levene's test was used to evaluate the homogeneity of variance. For intergroup comparisons, the independent t-test was employed to determine statistical significance between the two treatment groups. Chi-square tests were used for the comparison of ordinal and nominal variables, particularly to assess associations in categorical data.

The following statistical formulas were applied:

Mean: calculated as the sum of all scores divided by the number of observations.

Range: computed as the difference between the highest and lowest scores.

Variance and Standard Deviation : used to measure data dispersion around the mean.

Independent t-test : used to compare the means between two independent groups and determine if the difference is statistically significant.

Chi-square test: used to test the goodness of fit and evaluate the association between categorical variables by comparing observed and expected frequencies.

This statistical approach ensured reliable and valid interpretation of the data, allowing objective comparison between the two treatment modalities for temporomandibular joint disorder management.

Radiograph

Figure 3 - Orthopantomogram

Figure 4 - TMJ Open and Close View

Intraoperative Picture

Figure 5 - Landmark (holmlund-hellsing Line)

Figure 6 - TMJ Lavage

Figure 7 - Mouth

**Group II
Pre-operative Picture**

Figure 8 - Mouth

Radiograph

Figure 9 - Orthopantomogram

Figure 10 - TMJ Open and Close

**Intra-operative Picture
Post-operative 1 Month Picture**

Figure 11 - Landmark (holmlund-hellsing)

Figure 12 - TMJ Lavage

Figure 13 - Mouth Opening

Results

In terms of gender distribution, Group 1 consisted of 20% females and 80% males, while Group 2 included 60% females and 40% males.

Regarding pain scores, both groups showed improvement over time. The pre-treatment mean pain score was 6.60 in Group 1 and 7.00 in Group 2. On the 7th postoperative day, the mean scores reduced to 3.80 and 4.40, respectively. Although Group 1 showed a slightly greater reduction in pain, the difference between the two groups was statistically non-significant ($p = 0.759$). By the 4th week, the mean pain score further decreased to 1.40 in Group 1 and 3.00 in Group 2, showing a statistically significant difference in favour of Group 1 ($p = 0.021$).

In the comparison of mouth opening, Group 1 showed a mean pre-treatment value of 27.60 mm, which increased to 33.20 mm at day 7 and 39.00 mm at the 4th week. Group 2 started with a higher baseline of 31.20 mm, which improved to 35.40 mm at day 7 and 37.60 mm at week 4. Although the difference was not significant at day 7 ($p = 0.443$), it became statistically significant at the 4th week ($p = 0.016$), indicating better mouth opening in Group 1.

In terms of pain on lateral movement, 100% of patients in Group 1 and 60% in Group 2 reported pain at baseline. By the 7th day, only 20% in Group 1 and 40% in Group 2 reported pain. At the 4th week, none of the patients in either group experienced pain during lateral movement. The intergroup differences at all time points were statistically non-significant.

TMJ clicking was present in 40% of Group 1 and 80% of Group 2 at baseline. By day 7, it was reduced to 20% in Group 1 and 40% in Group 2. At the 4th week, no clicking was reported in either group. The reduction was clinically noticeable but statistically non-significant throughout the evaluation period.

Anxiety scores also decreased in both groups. Group 1 showed a pre-treatment mean anxiety score of 8.20, reducing to 4.40 at day 7 and 2.00 at week 4. Group 2 started at 7.60, reduced to 5.60 at day 7 and 3.00 at week 4. The intergroup comparison showed a non-significant difference at day 7 ($p = 0.133$), but a statistically significant difference at week 4 ($p = 0.021$), with greater improvement observed in Group 1.

Overall, both treatment modalities showed improvement in TMJ pain and function, but Group 1 (arthrocentesis with dulo-

xetine) demonstrated more significant and sustained reductions in pain, better mouth opening, and greater reduction in anxiety over the 4 week period.

Discussion

Temporomandibular joint disorder (TMD) was initially described by Hey et al.¹ as a localized mechanical fault disrupting the smooth function of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ). TMD is now widely recognized as a group of musculoskeletal and neuromuscular conditions involving the TMJ, masticatory muscles, and surrounding tissues². These disorders often lead to significant clinical symptoms including pain, restricted mandibular movement, joint noises (clicking or crepitus), and in many cases, psychological distress.

The current study was undertaken to assess and compare the clinical efficacy of duloxetine and amitriptyline, both centrally acting medications, when used as adjuncts to arthrocentesis in managing patients with internal derangement of the TMJ. Arthrocentesis is a minimally invasive procedure that helps in flushing inflammatory mediators, releasing adhesions, and restoring normal joint mobility. The focus was particularly on patients diagnosed with Wilkes Stage II and III disorders, which typically involve anterior disc displacement with and without reduction³.

Wilkes' classification system³ provides a crucial framework for understanding disease progression from early stages involving mild disc displacement and occasional pain (Stage I & II) to advanced stages marked by severe disc deformation and degenerative bony changes (Stage IV & V). These progressive stages highlight the importance of early intervention. In our study, arthrocentesis combined with centrally acting agents was performed on patients primarily in early stages to arrest progression and alleviate symptoms.

Pain, the cardinal symptom of TMD, results from both peripheral and central mechanisms. Peripheral sources include inflammation of the retrodiscal tissues and muscles, while centrally, altered neurotransmitter activity plays a role. Singh et al.² conducted a study comparing arthrocentesis, duloxetine therapy alone, and their combination. They concluded that the combination therapy offered superior pain relief. Similarly, Kumar et al.⁴ observed that duloxetine, a serotonin norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor (SNRI), significantly enhanced pain control when used adjunctively with arthrocentesis. Supporting evidence from Nitzan et al.⁵ and Yura & Totsuka⁶ emphasized that arthrocentesis itself plays a vital role in reducing intra-articular pressure and washing out inflammatory mediators, thus directly relieving joint pain. In our findings, both groups showed pain reduction postoperatively, but the Group I (Duloxetine + Arthrocentesis) exhibited significantly better outcomes at the fourth week ($p = 0.021$), suggesting the potential central action of duloxetine in reducing chronic pain.

Maximum mouth opening (MMO) is a key clinical measure to assess the improvement in joint function. Nitzan et al.⁵ first demonstrated the utility of arthrocentesis in treating patients with restricted mouth opening. Malik and Shah also supported these findings and highlighted the long-term improvement in jaw mobility after joint lavage. Furthermore, Singh et al.² and Kumar et al.⁴ reported that duloxetine significantly contributes to improved MMO, likely due to pain modulation and reduction in muscle tension. In our study, the Group I patients showed greater improvement in MMO compared to Group II at the fourth week, with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.016$), reinforcing the idea that duloxetine may be more effective than amitriptyline in enhancing functional mobility post arthrocentesis.

Lateral jaw movement, though less emphasized in many studies, is vital for normal masticatory function. Yura and Totsuka⁶ found that arthrocentesis improved all components of mandibular motion, including lateral excursions. List and Jensen⁸ proposed that pharmacological interventions aimed at central pain mechanisms may improve jaw dynamics indirectly by reducing associated myofascial pain and muscular tension. Our results indicated a trend toward improvement in lateral movement across both groups, but the difference was not statistically significant, suggesting that while joint lavage contributes to improved mobility, neither drug had a marked differential effect on this parameter.

Joint clicking, a common clinical sign of disc displacement with reduction, was present in several patients at baseline. Moses et al.⁹ in their arthroscopic study observed improved disc mobility and joint function in the majority of patients following surgical lavage, though they did not directly measure sound. Yura and Totsuka⁶ demonstrated that sufficient hydraulic pressure during arthrocentesis could eliminate clicking by restoring disc-condyle coordination. In our study, TMJ clicking decreased in both groups by the fourth week, but no statistically significant difference was observed between groups, suggesting that improvement was primarily due to the mechanical effect of arthrocentesis.

The psychological impact of TMD is increasingly recognized. Chronic orofacial pain is often associated with anxiety, depression, and impaired quality of life. Zigmond and Snaith¹⁰ developed the HADS scale, which has become a standard tool to assess psychological distress in medical settings. Santos et al.¹¹ evaluated amitriptyline's efficacy in TMD patients and found improvements in both pain and psychological parameters, particularly when combined with cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT). However, duloxetine has a more robust dual action on serotonin and norepinephrine pathways, which has shown efficacy in chronic pain conditions such as fibromyalgia and diabetic neuropathy, as seen in the study by Thor et al.¹² In our analysis, Group I (duloxetine) patients exhibited a greater reduction in anxiety scores, with statistical significance at the fourth week ($p = 0.021$), highlighting duloxetine's superior central action in relieving psychological comorbidities associated with TMD.

Conclusion

The treatment of internal derangement temporomandibular joint has sparked widespread debates because no consensus has been reached. When conservative therapy fails, minimally invasive procedures such as arthrocentesis were recommended. There were various medications available to reduce temporomandibular joint pain, Duloxetine had been used in various fields of modern medicine for its invaluable useful properties and only a very few studies had been conducted to assess its role in internal derangement of TMJ. Our study had concluded that use of combination of duloxetine with arthrocentesis gave an outcome much better than Amitriptyline with arthrocentesis of TMJ in controlling the pain. The maximum incisal mouth opening was better with Duloxetine group with arthrocentesis than Amitriptyline group with arthrocentesis of TMJ. Clicking sounds were reduced in Duloxetine group than Amitriptyline group. Anxiety and depression were reduced in Duloxetine group than Amitriptyline group. Further studies with large sample size must evaluate the effect of arthrocentesis combined with duloxetine in providing permanent relief to the patient.

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